

**ULUG'BEK HAMDAM NASRIDA YOLG'IZLIK MOTIVI
МОТИВ ОДИНОЧИЯ В ПРОЗЕ УЛУГБЕКА ХАМДАМА
THE MOTIF OF LONELINESS IN ULUGBEK HAMDAM'S PROSE**

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Annotatsiya

Istiqlof davri qissachiligida Ulug'bek Hamdam "Yolg'izlik" qissasi bilan adabiy jamoatchilik va keng kitobxonlar ommasi e'tiboriga tushdi. Qissada insonning ruhiy olami, uning rango-rang tuyg'ularining tajassumini yoritish borasida katta yutuqlarga erishilganligi yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi. Ijodkor yolg'izlikni asar sarlavhasidan motiv darajasiga olib chiqqanligi asarda aks etgan.

Tayanch so'z va iboralar: motiv, modernizm, qissa, ruhiyat, voqea, portret, monolog, dialog, tush, peyzaj, dialektika.

Аннотация

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В новелле периода независимости Улугбек Хамдам привлек внимание литературной общественности и широкой читательской аудитории повестью "Одиночество". В повести ясно показано, что достигнуты большие успехи в выяснении духовного мира человека, воплощении его эмоций. В произведении отражено то, что одиночество художник вывел из названия произведения на уровень мотива.

Ключевые слова и выражения: Ключевые слова и фразы: мотив, модернизм, рассказ, психика, событие, портрет, монолог, диалог, мечта, пейзаж, диалектика.

Abstract

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In the short story of the independence period, Ulugbek Hamdam came to the attention of the literary community and a wide readership with the story "Loneliness". In the story, it is clearly shown that great progress has been made in elucidating the spiritual world of a person, the embodiment of his emotions. It is reflected in the work that the artist took loneliness from the title of the work to the level of motive.

Key words and word expressions: Key words and phrases: motive, modernism, story, psyche, event, portrait, monologue, dialogue, dream, landscape, dialectic.

INTRODUCTION

Several studies have been conducted in world literature on the motif of "Loneliness". In particular, the works of scientists such as B. Massey, B. Middleton, A. Worsley, H. Gibson, P. Laslet were published. Psychologist Sigmund Freud explains the causes of alienation in human nature from a scientific point of view in his work "Civilization and Protests". Among the Uzbek scientists, the doctoral work of H. Umurov, A. Kholmurodov and P. Kenjayeva, Kilicheva Mehriniso's candidacy studies focused on the research of psychic charms. For example, Kilicheva Mehriniso in her candidacy research "The problem of literary influence in the interpretation of psychological situations in English and Uzbek literature" emphasizes that the motif of loneliness first met in F. Petrarch's work "The Life of Solitude". For the first time in Uzbek literature, it is stated that this motif is reflected in Yusuf Hos Hajib's work "Kutadgu Bilig" when Ozgurmish takes the path of solitude and realizes the reality of life alone. Also, in the literary studies of the 21st century, R. Saidova's treatise "Aql va ruh Bakhsi" contains comments on the interpretation of the motif of loneliness.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In Uzbek literature, from ancient times to examples of folklore, in the examples of modern literature, a strong sense of negative coloring towards loneliness can be felt. It is known that Allah created all living beings in pairs. Since ancient times, it has been said that there is goodness in living in pairs, and loneliness is characteristic of being alone. In our classical literature, the motif of loneliness is mainly used in the meanings of retreating to the bliss and purifying the soul. "The largest percentage of human sufferings are connected with invisible webs of abstract and ambiguous feelings, so that the human generation, busy with life's worries, does not even try to understand and understand the nature of such situations. Perhaps many people do not even try because they realize that this action is ineffective. But there is a category of people. They are doomed to think about a very complex and complicated process. This category is commonly referred to as the people of the pen and the people of creativity" [1;159]. Such masterpieces are created by such creative people. It is known that the artistic world of artists is formed on the basis of their life reality. U. Hamdam is one of our creators who was able to bring such reality into his artistic world. In the writer's short story "Loneliness", a diverse image of the human psyche is expressed from different angles. In our literature, the relationship between the spirit and the event is one of the primary features of the artistic work. The achievements of prose works, especially short stories, are being evaluated by the level of mental imagery, and it seems that the role of the epic narration has waned. In particular, in realistic stories, the epic narrative is primary, while in non-traditional stories, psychological analysis takes the main place. Although these two components are related to each other, one of them takes the lead in the image. The characteristic

attitude of this situation is manifested by the priority of the psyche in the story “Loneliness” by U. Hamdam, which is the object of our research. B.Karim, Q.Yoldoshev, R.Rahmat, among our literary scholars, expressed their opinions about the work. For example, Kazoqboy Yoldoshev: In the story “Loneliness” exactly the chaos, not in reality, but the chaos in human imagination and experiences is depicted: Rather, it is the idea of giving an irregular and random flow of thoughts. looks at it as an artistic goal. It is known that there is no consistency and regularity in imagination. That’s why a person is guided by the imagination, not the imagination” [2:511]. B. Karimov agrees with Q. Yoldoshev: “Loneliness” is not dedicated to the artistic interpretation of a certain interesting event, it does not contain traditional images, images, landscapes, dialogues: it is a monologue story. In this sense, “Loneliness” appeared as a product of enthusiastic and depressed, thoughtful and thoughtless moods, nameless sufferings in the human psyche” [3;3].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

B.Karim, Q.Yoldoshev, R.Rahmat, among our literary scholars, expressed their opinions about the work. For example, Kazoqboy Yoldoshev: In the story “Loneliness” exactly the chaos, not in reality, but the chaos in human imagination and experiences is depicted: Rather, it is the idea of giving an irregular and random flow of thoughts. looks at it as an artistic goal. It is known that there is no consistency and regularity in imagination. That's why a person is guided by the imagination, not the imagination" [4:511]. B. Karimov agrees with Q. Yoldoshev: “Loneliness” is not dedicated to the artistic interpretation of a certain interesting event, it does not contain traditional images, images, landscapes, dialogues: it is a monologue story. In this sense, “Loneliness” appeared as a product of enthusiastic and depressed, thoughtful and thoughtless moods, nameless sufferings in the human psyche” [5;511].

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that U. Hamdam is one of the creators who brought the motif of loneliness to the title level. Solitude reflected in the story “Loneliness” is reflected as a psychological state that purifies a person, invites him to enlightenment, helps him understand the essence of life, and encourages him to rise through contemplation. The artist skillfully used the elements of modernism and was able to reveal the image of the psyche on a large scale. Loneliness appears in the work as a motive that cleanses the human heart and leads to enlightenment.

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